

HIGH-POWER AND SAFE RF WIRELESS CHARGING: CAUTIOUS DEPLOYMENT AND OPERATION

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ABSTRACT

Wired charging and the need for battery replacements are critical barriers to unlimited, scalable, and sustainable mobile connectivity, motivating the interest in radio frequency (RF) wireless power transfer (WPT) technology. However, the inherently low end-to-end power transfer efficiency (PTE) and health/safety-related apprehensions about the technology are critical obstacles. Indeed, RF-WPT implementation and operation require efficient and cautious strategies and protocols, especially when targeting high-power charging, which constitutes the scope of this work. Herein, we overview the main factors affecting the end-to-end PTE of RF-WPT systems and their multiplicative effect and interdependencies. Moreover, we discuss key electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure metrics, safety limits, and approaches for efficient and EMF-aware deployment and operation. Quantitatively, we show that near-field RF charging may significantly reduce EMF exposure, and thus must be promoted. We also present our vision of a cyber-physical system for efficient and safe wireless charging, specify key components and their interrelation, and illustrate numerically the PTE attained by two modern low-power multi-antenna architectures in a simple setup. Throughout the article, we highlight the need for high end-to-end PTE architectures and charging protocols transparently complying with EMF exposure regulations, and outline relevant challenges and research directions. This work expands the vision and understanding of modern RF-WPT technology and constitutes a step toward making the technology attractive for worldwide commercial exploitation.

INTRODUCTION

The wired charging and the need for battery replacements are critical barriers to unlimited, scalable, and sustainable mobile connectivity. Ubiquitous wired charging is usually cost-prohibitive, especially in industrial Internet of Things (IoT) deployments, while battery-powered solutions struggle with limited battery life and the replacement problem, which is neither economical nor eco-friendly. Industry and academia agree that ambient energy harvesting (EH) and wireless power transfer (WPT) paradigms may overcome this shortly [1]. Notably, WPT may be inevitably needed in applications with quality-of-service

(QoS) requirements since EH from ambient energy is non-deterministic and location-dependent, often requiring relatively large form factor transducers.

WPT solutions widely available in the market rely on short-range reactive techniques exploiting magnetic/electric fields with limited multi-user support and still confining the maneuverability, mobility, and scalability of the device(s) charged. Conversely, radiative radio frequency (RF)-WPT technology natively supports multiuser charging and allows greater charging radii [1]. However, its inherently low end-to-end power transfer efficiency (PTE) and safety-related apprehensions are critical obstacles, hindering standardization activities. These have motivated mostly customized low-power IoT charging applications relying on energy beamforming (EBF) and waveform optimization [2–6]; distributed and massive antenna systems [4]; smart reflect arrays and metasurfaces [7, 6]; and flexible energy transmitters (ETs) [1] (i.e., moving ETs and ETs with rotary antennas); while in many cases explicitly incorporating electromagnetic field (EMF) radiation exposure control [2, 4]. We believe a comprehensive combination and holistic optimization of these promising technologies (and others) are crucial for competitive RF-WPT efficiency, expanding the market to higher-power charging applications. Indeed, startups such as Energous, Ossia, and GuRu are leaping forward with RF-WPT solutions that are not restricted to this regime.

Although RF-WPT is rapidly gaining market, its implementation and operation still require cautious strategies and protocols. Herein, we elaborate further on this while making the following contributions:

- We overview the main factors affecting the PTE of RF-WPT systems and their interrelation, calling for joint optimization approaches.
- We overview key EMF exposure metrics and safety limits, and discuss approaches for EMF-awareness. We illustrate the effect of frequency and far/near-field conditions on EMF exposure manageability, showing that near-field RF charging may significantly reduce EMF exposure.
- We envision a cyber-physical system (CPS)¹ for efficient/safe WPT while specifying key components and their interrelation. We illustrate the PTE attained by two low-power MIMO

¹ CPSs intertwine physical systems with embedded, real-time computations, enabling autonomous decision-making and actions in complex environments.

FIGURE 1. Block diagram of the architecture of an RF-WPT system and main energy consumption/loss sources.

architectures, showing that reflective intelligent surface (RIS) and dynamic metasurface antenna (DMA)-based ETs may attain similar performance, also in terms of EMF radiation manageability.

- We highlight relevant challenges throughout the article while pointing to potential research directions.

Reproducible research: Simulation codes are available at: <https://github.com/onel2428/High-Power-and-Safe-WPT>.

RF-WPT TECHNOLOGY AND KEY CONCERNS

Figure 1 illustrates RF-WPT system architecture, comprising ETs, wireless channels, and energy receivers (ERs). On the ET side, the charging signal is generated in the digital domain and converted to analog by the digital-to-analog converter (DAC). This is followed by RF upconversion, signal amplification supported by a high-power amplifier (HPA), and wireless transmission using an antenna array. On the ER side, the impinging charging signal, distorted by the channel, is captured by the receive antenna(s) and converted to DC via a rectifying network. A matching network between the antenna(s) and the rectifying circuitry maximizes the power transfer at a designed frequency band [1, 3]. These blocks compose the so-called rectenna. Then, the rectified signal goes through a power management unit (PMU), which may include a DC-to-DC converter and energy storage. Finally, the PMU interfaces with the energy demands of the device.

Next, we discuss the two main RF-WPT concerns. Their effective resolution is crucial to boosting the technology's appeal and fostering standardization, guaranteeing interoperability and market accessibility.

LOW END-TO-END PTE

RF charging is slower and less efficient than traditional wired and reactive wireless charging due to the many sources of energy consumption and loss, as depicted in Fig. 1.

The main energy consumption sources at the ET are the baseband processing, including digital signal generation and DAC controller; carrier gen-

eration; and HPA DC supply. In general, DAC and HPA power consumption dominate. DAC's power consumption increases with the desired analog signal resolution, including the number of quantization levels and sampling rate, thus the operation frequency. HPA's efficiency is typically below 60 percent, so significant DC power is lost as heat. Meanwhile, energy management at the PMU and transceiver operation, including signal processing in closed-loop implementations, may dominate on the ER side. Antenna array controlling circuitry may consume additional energy at both ET and ER.

The main energy losses come from filtering processes, channel impairments, and the receive antenna aperture. Filtering may be applied:

- After DAC, to remove high-frequency components
- After upconversion, to remove parasite frequency components
- After HPA, to remove frequency components introduced by the HPA non-linearity
- In the matching network, since frequency components outside its operation bandwidth are removed or attenuated
- After the rectifier, to remove the fundamental and harmonic frequencies of the rectified signal.

In all cases, energy outside the desired frequency band is lost. Meanwhile, the channel impairments encompass path loss, fading, shadowing, and non-line-of-sight conditions. Even in free-space (favorable) conditions, the power density of a signal decreases quadratically with the distance, causing the most relevant efficiency loss in typical systems. Moreover, the amount of power captured from a radiation field is proportional to the antenna aperture, which increases quadratically with the wavelength and linearly with the antenna gain. Nevertheless, given a receive antenna with a fixed form factor, one can equip more/fewer antenna elements for higher/lower operation frequency, thus, reducing aperture losses.

Other energy losses may come from:

- Elements insertion in non-integrated circuits
- Transmit-receive polarization mismatches
- Energy storage leakage
- Energy dissipation at resistive elements, switching, conduction, reverse-recovery, and parasitic capacitance/inductance.

metric	exposure zone	averaging time (min)	frequency range	
			2–6 GHz	6–300 GHz
incident power density (W/m ²)	whole body	30	10	10
	local	6	40	55/f(GHz) ^{0.177}
incident energy density (kJ/m ²)	local	t(t < 6)	14.4 × (0.05 + 0.95√t/6)	19.8 × (0.05 + 0.95√t/6) / f(GHz) ^{0.177}

TABLE 1. EMF exposure limits for the general public at high frequencies according to ICNIRP.

Notice that the efficiency of each block in the RF-WPT system multiplicatively impacts the overall PTE. The performance of the blocks may exhibit dependence, so optimizing them independently is not optimal. For instance:

- DAC's power consumption increases with the required resolution while lower DAC resolutions trigger the generation of high-frequency components to be filtered out, leading to energy loss.
- In multi-tone charging waveforms, the more sub-carriers, the greater the flexibility to optimize the waveform to drive the HPA and rectenna to high-efficiency regimes [3], but the greater the signal processing energy consumption.
- Reducing the number of transmit RF chains is appealing for reducing the transmit energy consumption but limits the EBF gains and the multi-user charging capabilities.

These fundamental trade-offs require attention during design and operation. Moreover, an efficient high-power RF-WPT system requires closed-loop operation with a reverse/forward communication link to acquire channel state information (CSI) and combat channel impairments [2–5]. More evolved optimizations require bidirectional communication links supporting a control plane.

EMF EXPOSURE CONCERNS

RF transmissions are non-ionizing, thus cannot directly alter the structure of molecules leading to carcinogenic effects. However, this does not discard potential indirect links. The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) classified RF emissions as “possibly carcinogenic to humans” [8].² This does not indicate that RF emissions definitively cause cancer, but that there is (limited) evidence suggesting a possible link. Nevertheless, mild biological effects such as tissue heating are known to occur when exposed to very strong EMFs at microwave frequencies or higher.

EMF exposure limits have been set by regulatory bodies, for example, the United States Federal Communications Commission (FCC) and Food & Drug Administration (FDA), to mitigate the potential adverse effects on human health. The regulations aim to balance the risks and benefits of RF technologies and are regularly reviewed and updated. There are also standard bodies, for example, the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), American National Standards Institute (ANSI), Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), and International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP). Their recommendations, though not legally enforceable, are typically adopted by regulators.

EMF exposure metrics such as specific absorption rate (SAR, in W/kg), specific absorption (SA, in kJ/kg), absorbed power density (APD, in

W/m²), and absorbed energy density (AED, in kJ/m²) correspond to physical quantities that are closely related to RF-induced biological effects. SAR and SA are valid for systems operating below 6 GHz, where EMFs penetrate deep into the tissue. Meanwhile, APD and AED are more useful above 6 GHz where penetration depth is less relevant [9]. However, all these may not be easily measured/estimated in practice. Other related quantities that are more easily evaluated are the incident power density (in W/m²), incident energy density (kJ/m²), electric field strength (in V/m), and magnetic field strength (in A/m). EMF exposure limits are usually conservatively set in terms of them such that SAR, SA, APD, and AED remain below the safety limits with extremely high reliability [9].

High-power RF charging may be possible only for short ranges as channel losses escalate with the distance. In short-range scenarios, precise (highly focused) spatial charging is needed to avoid increased EMF exposure levels in the ER surroundings. This may be only achieved by operating at high frequencies and in the massive MIMO regime [4], but also in the near-field region of the ETs [5].

Table 1 compiles EMF exposure limits for the general public according to ICNIRP.³ The EMF limits decrease slowly with the operation frequency above 6 GHz in both incident power and energy densities. Moreover, the incident power density limit is far more stringent for local exposure zones than for the whole body, for which the averaging time is also greater.

Consider the setup illustrated in Fig. 2a, where a 10 × 10 antenna array charges a device located $d = 8$ m away in its boresight direction. The array is square with horizontally/vertically equally-spaced antennas. We let the edge length, denoted by L , scale as a function of the wavelength λ and the near-far-field threshold distance d' such that $d' = L^2/\lambda$. The latter is a common threshold between near and far field conditions, that is, $d < d'(d > d') \rightarrow$ near (far) field. In Fig. 2b, we show the incident power density at a distance r from the receive antenna, that is, in the r -radius sphere centered at the receive antenna. The results are normalized by the RF power delivered to the device to facilitate insight extrapolation. High EMF exposure levels may come from high spatial correlation, which decreases with r . Therefore, the incident power density decreases with r (as shown also in [4]), especially under near-field conditions (large d'). Notably, local EMF exposure under far-field conditions escalates if the living tissues are between the antenna array and the ER since beams are strictly directional, calling for beam avoidance mechanisms [2]. This is not a problem as near-field conditions intensify, that is, by decreasing d/d' , since the RF energy reaches the receiver from a

² This classification corresponds to Group 2B. Group 1, 2A, and 3 correspond to agents that are “carcinogenic,” “probably carcinogenic,” and “not classifiable as to its carcinogenicity” to humans, respectively [8].

³ Europe and FCC mostly follow ICNIRP recommendations for EMF exposure limits. The limits illustrated in Table 1 for occupational scenarios are five-fold less stringent than for the general public. This is because individuals in occupational scenarios know the potential EMF risks and employ appropriate harm-mitigation measures.

broader array of spatial directions and is sharply focused on the receive antenna.

The frequency impact in Fig. 2b is significantly less obvious: given a number of antennas, the EMF exposure can be more easily controlled at relatively high (low) frequencies in far (near)-field conditions. If the antenna count increases with frequency, the resulting higher spatial resolution at high frequencies aids in managing EMF exposure [4]. However, increasing the number of antennas in a small-scale setup may not be efficient/viable, which motivates the illustrated results. We have also delimited in Fig. 2b the local exposure limits according to ICNIRP (Table 1). For this, we assume 1 W RF power at the device and uninterrupted transmissions such that 6-min averaging aligns with instantaneous results. Notably, in extreme near-field conditions such that $d' \geq 15$ m, the incident EMF exposure stays within the safety limits for $r \leq 1.8$ cm and $f \leq 30$ GHz. This might be enough for safely charging a phone in human hands if the receive antenna and phone are properly placed and held.

The above results are for local incident power density. Getting quantitative insights on the whole-body EMF exposure, for example, for a person holding the device, may be much more intricate as it depends on the body's build. A child holding the ER would have much more EMF exposure than an adult as the entire body is closer to the device. Estimating the incident power density for the whole body in near-field conditions is open for research, and conservative methodologies may be preferred. It might be easier to compute volumetric, rather than area, power/energy densities, but this either requires some research on corresponding EMF exposure limit values or proper procedures for quantities conversions.

Note that incident energy density exposure constraints are set to avoid high power density peaks for several minutes, which would still meet incident power density constraints. However, if the instantaneous incident power density remains below or equal to the 6-min average value, the incident energy density constraint is certainly met. In any case, the 6-min averaging of power and energy densities gives some flexibility to potential charging protocols and thus must be explored with dedicated research. All in all, cautious deployment/operation strategies for RF-WPT systems providing transparent EMF radiation exposure guarantees for the end users are needed.

CPS FOR EFFICIENT AND SAFE WIRELESS CHARGING

The key components of a competitive indoor WPT CPS are transmitters, intelligent reflectors, harvesters, auxiliary nodes, management systems, and charging protocols. These are discussed below, while Fig. 3 illustrates their interaction and two key application scenarios. A proper holistic design of these components, although challenging, is critical to unleashing the full potential of RF-WPT and turning it into a sustainable wireless charging technology, bringing the attention of the market, and propitiating more standardization attempts and commercial products.

TRANSMITTERS AND INTELLIGENT REFLECTORS

Massive MIMO deployments can compensate for the huge channel losses, promote near-field conditions, and support ubiquitous energy access [1, 4]. However, the high manufacturing and operating

FIGURE 2. a) Simulation setup: a fully digital transmit antenna array charges a single-antenna ER. b) Incident RF power density at a distance r from the ER and normalized by the RF power delivered to the device. Results are presented for three operation frequencies and near-far-field thresholds d' considering purely geometrical channels. EMF limits for local exposure according to ICNIRP values are illustrated by red lines and * markers.

expenses and power consumption of truly large-scale antenna arrays pose challenges, driving research into cost-effective and low-power MIMO architectures, potentially powered by ambient EH sources [10].

Hybrid analog-digital MIMO implementations require fewer power-consuming RF chains, while further power reductions can be achieved using low-resolution DACs. In the analog domain, antenna selection architectures, parasitic, load-modulated, and lens arrays are viable. Metasurface-aided architectures, for example, RIS and large intelligent surface (LIS), constitute another key research front to support low-power/cost MIMO [6, 7, 11].

RISs can boost MIMO networks by dynamically reconfiguring the wireless medium, steering the power to the intended ER(s) by adjusting transmit signals' phase, amplitude, frequency, and polarization. Conventional RISs comprise fully passive reflecting elements. The only active power consumption comes from a controller, allowing energy-efficient implementations without incorporating additional RF radiation into the environment. However, the performance gains may be limited given relatively few reflective elements. This has motivated the research on active RIS [11, 12], where the reflecting elements incorporate reflection-type

FIGURE 3. Our vision for a competitive RF-WPT system and two key scenarios: room/office and industrial IoT. Charging arrows only indicate the transmission origin since charging may be highly spatial-focused in the near field. Colored textboxes outline how the CPS elements contribute to efficient and safe wireless charging and their main challenges.

amplifiers without high-cost and power-hungry RF chains. Such active circuitry allows simultaneously altering the phase and amplitude to enhance the signal power at the receiver. Nevertheless, they incur modestly higher power consumption and require evolved CSI acquisition procedures. Identifying passive vs active RISs performance trade-offs in the context of RF-WPT, where noise power is not an issue, is open for research. For instance, initial insights from [12] reveal how the effectiveness of passive/active RIS implementations varies for wireless information transmission (WIT) versus RF-WPT in a multi-RIS downlink system. In general, further assessment studies should consider overhead and protocol issues.

Meanwhile, LISs are low-power/cost massive MIMO metasurfaces with RF circuits and signal processing units. They are composed of a virtually infinite number of elements to form a spatially continuous transceiver aperture. LISs can be realized using an RIS illuminated by a collocated digital beamforming-based transmitter [13]. RIS reconfigurability provides extra degrees of freedom in this implementation, enabling scaling the number of passive elements without increasing the number of active antennas. Meanwhile, DMA, another LIS implementation, comprises multiple waveguides, for example, microstrip, and each may embed a large set of radiating metamaterial elements whose frequency response can be externally adjusted [6]. One or several RF chains can feed the waveguides, while metamaterial elements radiate the input signals.

Figure 4 illustrates the power consumption of RIS/DMA-based ETs as a function of frequency for a single-ER setup together with the power density at 15 cm from the ER. Note that RIS and DMA-based architectures exhibit similar performance. Still, a RIS-based ET seems preferable at lower frequencies, although it may be more costly than DMA's. All this depends on the scenario geometry and the number of ERs. We refer the reader to [6, 10, 13] for interesting research directions. Interestingly, the

performance of RIS-based ETs with only two control bits per element is near optimal (obtained with infinite-resolution RIS). Meanwhile, increasing the operation frequency is appealing for satisfying the EMF radiation exposure constraints given a fixed form factor and charging distance. Indeed, ICNIRP regulations are met for frequencies above 6.2 GHz in both RIS and DMA-based setups. A critical LIS optimization challenge arises with increasing frequency since the number of variables, that is, antenna elements' phase shifts configuration, becomes massive, overwhelming conventional optimization solvers. Two aggravating factors are that: for RIS, the phase shifts are discrete; and for DMA, more antenna elements can fit a certain form factor and they have a Lorentzian-form response [6]. Based on the illustrated results and after dealing with the previous challenges, one can speculate that end-to-end PTEs in the order of 10 percent may be realized when using greater form-factor LIS-based ETs.

Finally, the most investigated metasurfaces are those for passive beamforming/reflection applications. Other metamaterial functions such as refraction, absorption, collimation, polarization change, splitting, and analog processing can be software-engineered using accurate physics-compliant models to promote more flexible and dynamic metasurface-based WPT implementations. Moreover, distributing WPT antennas and metasurfaces over the charging area, though ideal, is not often aesthetically or economically attractive. It is more appealing favoring imperceptible installation via hybrid deployments of distributed and centralized arrays, for example, using radio stripes [4], together with scenario-specific metasurface assemblage. Using hardware-flexible ETs such as motor-equipped and flying ETs may be attractive.

HARVESTERS

The ER circuit blocks must be properly designed for high RF power at the desired frequencies. Multi-stage rectifiers using Schottky diodes are attractive for this due to their low forward voltage drop and fast switch-

ing characteristics. The higher the incident RF power targets, the greater the number of rectifying stages/diodes required. In such a large-scale signal regime, diodes' behavior is predominantly resistive, which may facilitate optimization concerning the small-scale signal regime where diodes behave non-linearly. Meanwhile, capacitors with low equivalent series resistance and high voltage ratings are appealing as they incur lower power losses and can safely/efficiently handle higher currents; help maintain a stable output voltage by reducing voltage droop or ripple; and respond quickly to changes in voltage, allowing for faster charging cycles in the charge pump circuit. Nevertheless, such capacitors may induce higher parasitic effects. Two other fundamental ways to increase the harvestable energy are increasing:

- The number of receive antennas, which requires either DC, RF, or hybrid combining mechanisms;⁴
- The frequency spectrum utilization via wide-band or multi-band transmissions.

The ER design can be complex when weighing form factor and cost, requiring simulation, prototyping, and iterative optimization. Increasing the antenna's effective size may incur higher cost and complexity and increase the EMF radiation exposure above the safety limits locally (Fig. 2a) if the RF charging gains do not scale proportionally. Interestingly, metamaterials-based ERs constitute a promising research direction for realizing ultra-compact and high-efficiency ERs (see [7] and references therein). Small form factors can be realized due to the sub-wavelength periodicity of the unit cells within the lattice structure. A wide-beamwidth and polarization-independent operation including built-in matching networks and intrinsically high antenna gains promote high efficiency. Nevertheless, this inherently supposes separating WPT and WIT functions, which may not be appealing.

AUXILIARY NODES

Auxiliary nodes such as thermal sensors, light detection and ranging (LIDAR), radars, and cameras can assist in sensing and locating target ERs, (non-)living obstacles. Sensing and positioning services can support EMF-compliant exposure guarantees by detecting the presence of living species and accordingly tuning/disabling the high-power RF-WPT service.

Although ET deployments with/without a co-existent communication infrastructure may support sensing and/or positioning services via basic integrated sensing and communication (ISAC), additional accuracy guarantees are desired. These can be provided by a low-complexity sensing infrastructure, especially when living species do not carry devices, via device-free localization/sensing [14]. The on-demand sensing infrastructure availability and degenerative impact of imperfect sensing information on EMF radiation exposure must be considered to provide risk-aware guarantees. Finally, such auxiliary nodes could incorporate RF sensing capabilities helping to establish RF energy maps and efficient control charging services and EMF exposure.

CHARGING PROTOCOLS AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The charging protocols include WPT and WIT signaling and rely on information from the control plane. WIT signaling among ETs and ERs is required for CSI acquisition, charging requests, accurate positioning and sensing, and mobile edge computing (MEC) such that the devices can

FIGURE 4. a) Simulation setup: RIS/DMA-based ET charges a single-antenna ER located 3 m in the boresight direction; b) ETs' power consumption and power density at 15 cm from the ER, receiving 1 W of RF power, as a function of the frequency. A particle swarm optimization solver is utilized for the scenarios with finite-resolution RIS/DMA, while analog maximum ratio transmission is adopted for the scenarios with an infinite-resolution RIS-based ET.

fully/partially offload heavy computation tasks. MEC optimization should shift from minimizing devices' energy consumption to favor the effective system charging efficiency.

The charging protocols offer coordination and charging scheduling to increase the effective system PTE and comply with EMF exposure regulations. As illustrated in Fig. 5, the protocols depend on the scenario and the sophistication of the sensing infrastructure, which may be "low" if it merely detects human/animal presence in the area; "medium" if it also determines the position of the ERs and closest living species with limited accuracy; or "high" if it does that with high accuracy (e.g., cm-accuracy) and/or measures exposure data with wearables or sensors in human/animal's proximity.

For low-sophistication sensing infrastructures, high-power charging services are permitted only when the area is human/animal-free. A use case may be an industrial facility, wherein the RF charging service is deactivated upon a human detection. In the case of medium/high-sophistication sensing infrastructure, high-power charging services may be allowed even in the presence of humans as long as the estimated EMF exposure is safely limited. More sophisticated sensing demand more advanced ISAC systems.

⁴ In Fig. 1, we illustrate where RF and DC combining circuitry may be located within an ER. Notice that DC combining is purely passive, while RF combining may demand active circuitry to combine the RF signals coherently. Hybrid mechanisms trade off the pros and cons of pure DC and RF combining architectures and are preferred, especially when the number of receive antennas is large.

FIGURE 5. Illustration of different sophistication levels of the sensing infrastructure and charging approaches.

Charging requests may need to be secured and validated for micro-billing in public spaces while forecasting charging demands seems more convenient in massive industrial IoT. Proper charging scheduling may benefit significantly from accurate demand predictions. Scheduling simultaneous multi-device charging is advantageous in terms of efficiently exploiting the broadcast nature of the wireless medium, but makes it difficult to control the EMF exposure [4] and may be limited by maximum transmit power constraints. Flexible hybrid protocols considering the required charging time, for example, due to circuit-related constraints of RF harvesters and/or application demands, are needed.

The WPT management system, comprising local and global components, decides the charging protocols. The local management system (LM) interfaces with the physical WPT hardware while performing moderate-to-low complexity tasks such as CSI processing, charging request/forecast, EMF exposure estimation, edge computing, and small-scale optimization. Taming time-related dynamics such as the number of devices/humans in the loop, users in motion, time-varying energy demands, and computation requirements is essential. The LM should interface with the global management system (GM) component via QoS-constrained cloud links. GM manages large-scale optimization tasks, including evolved artificial intelligence (AI) mostly over long-term data, and can be used to keep the WPT hardware in the customer's facility simple/cheap. GM may provide substantial optimization gains by exploiting digital twins as testbed after taming cost, real-time integration, and data-hungry issues. Digital twins are virtual representations of physical systems, thus useful for simulating, analyzing, and optimizing complex CPSs, including ours.

The envisioned RF charging systems align with 6G in-X subnetworks [15], for example, in-house/room/plant RF-WPT subnetworks. The WPT system may either co-exist (separate functioning with dedicated infrastructure), cooperate (LM/ETs interface with the connectivity local service provider), or be co-designed (joint hardware/functioning and LM and GM support) with the wireless information network infrastructure while providing added

value. The third option is the final evolution step of a functional WPT system.

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Office spaces, manufacturing plants, residential settings, and more, benefit from seamless ubiquitous charging. In this article, we presented our vision for a high-power and safe RF charging CPS enabling such applications. We overviewed the main factors affecting the system's end-to-end PTE and EMF exposure. We showed that the EMF exposure close to the ER can be more easily controlled in near-field conditions. Unexpectedly, it can be more easily controlled at relatively high (low) frequencies in far (near)-field conditions given a fixed number of transmit antennas, and at high frequencies given form factor constraints.

We highlighted the need for high end-to-end PTE architectures and charging protocols transparently complying with EMF exposure regulations.

Key challenges and research directions from our overarching discussions are summarized thusly:

- Distributedly deploying WPT antennas and metasurfaces mitigates channel losses and promotes near-field conditions for better EMF management. Site surveys assessing charging area layouts, including user densities, and hybrid antenna deployments favoring aesthetics and low costs are essential. These require 3D modeling, channel analysis, optimization, and data analytics tools.
- Minimizing power consumption and costs simultaneously is challenging. For example, adding antennas increases EBF gains but also deployment costs, power consumption when incorporating additional RF chains, and overheating risks. PTE optimization plus optimized ET/RIS deployments, potentially incorporating ambient EH modules, are key.
- Increasing operation frequency allows more antennas within form factor limits, promoting near-field conditions but complicating system optimization due to non-linearities. Advanced signal processing and data-driven heuristics like sparse array processing and principal component analysis for dimensionality reduction are needed. Power/time requirements must be considered. Advanced simulations and testbeds are crucial for validating and refining algorithms.
- Efficient high-power ER circuits are needed, for example, exploiting multi-stage Schottky rectifiers, low-resistance high-voltage capacitors (despite potential parasitic effects), metamaterial-based manufacturing, and multiple antennas (thus higher frequencies), and considering ER form-factor constraints. Simulation, prototyping, and iterative optimization are required.
- Obtaining precise estimates of EMF radiation exposure is challenging. 3D and channel propagation modeling considering uncertainty is required, potentially enhanced by interpolating available on-spot RF measurements for added accuracy. Global is harder to characterize than local EMF exposure and thus may require alternative geometrical shapes of body modeling. Conservative estimation methodologies are preferable.
- Charging protocols must be optimized utilizing: explainable AI to promote transparency/trust, especially given EMF exposure constraints; domain knowledge integration to exploit mature models/approaches; and meta-learning

for efficient extrapolations in low-data scenarios. Digital twins can serve as GM testbeds, with MEC facilitating computation offloading. Advancements in the above areas will drive novel business models and use cases while unlocking valuable big-data insights and catalyzing emerging technologies.

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Distributedly deploying WPT antennas and metasurfaces mitigates channel losses and promotes near-field conditions for better EMF management. Site surveys assessing charging area layouts, including user densities, and hybrid antenna deployments favoring aesthetics and low costs are essential.